

UPPSALA
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Uppsala University's Action Plan under the ARRA Commitment

Table of contents

Action plan for Uppsala University's work with the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment	3
Background	3
Action plan	4
<i>Commitment 1: Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research</i>	5
<i>Commitment 2: Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators</i>	5
<i>Commitment 3: Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index</i>	6
<i>Commitment 4: Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment</i>	6
Follow-up and evaluation	6

Action plan for Uppsala University's work with the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment

Background

In April 2024, following a decision by the Vice-Chancellor, Uppsala University signed the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA) within the framework of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA). This commitment includes the development and publication of an institutional action plan.

The purpose of the action plan is to guide and support the University's efforts to further develop and enhance the assessment of research and researchers during the period 2025–2030.

Current assessment practices at Uppsala University in relation to CoARA's core commitments

The plan has been developed based on a comprehensive mapping of Uppsala University's current practices in relation to ARRA. This mapping was informed by interviews with key stakeholders, including both academic and administrative staff.

The findings indicate that the University's current approach to research assessment is already largely aligned with ARRA. The University's appointment regulations (UFV 2019/1842) include criteria beyond scientific merit. Pedagogical proficiency is a core requirement, along with the ability to engage in collaboration with the wider society through research and teaching. When relevant, clinical, administrative, and leadership competencies are also taken into account. Each faculty provides guidelines with further details and criteria.

The evaluation of research and researchers is primarily qualitative. In the recruitment and promotion of lecturers, peer review is a well-established practice, teaching demonstrations are commonly conducted, and interviews, along with reference checks, are increasingly used. Metrics such as the Journal Impact Factor and H-index are not applied as formal criteria in recruitment and promotion, and rankings do not influence recruitment decisions or resource allocation, but are mainly used for communication purposes.

The University's own meta-level research evaluations, *Quality and Renewal*, rely on qualitative assessment, including self-evaluations and peer-review, supported by bibliometrics and other performance indicators.

Also, the University already actively participates in the Swedish chapter of CoARA.

The mapping also confirms that assessment cultures vary across disciplines. As such, further development of assessment practices in line with ARRA should primarily be driven within disciplinary domains and faculties, ideally in dialogue with corresponding

faculties at other higher education institutions. This does not exclude the possibility of enhanced coordination and exchange of experiences across the University's domains and faculties, as well as support from HR. On the contrary, such collaboration and support are considered highly valuable and contribute significantly to the overall development.

Action plan

Naturally, the mapping has also identified gaps and areas for improvement. In response, University Management has prioritised a set of actions aimed at strengthening alignment with ARRA's four core commitments.

Each action specifies responsible unit(s) and timeline. When applicable, the University Administration provides relevant support in accordance with its rules of procedure and any specific decisions made for the respective actions.

Overall actions

This section includes overall actions to further support the University's engagement with CoARA at the national and international levels, improve internal knowledge about ARRA, and ensure that alignment with its core commitments is appropriately adjusted to disciplinary contexts.

Action	Responsible unit(s)	Timeline
1. Coordinate participation in working groups within the Swedish national chapter of CoARA and/or consider establishing direct representation in a strategic working group at the European CoARA level.	To be decided	2026-ongoing
2. Share insights on ARRA, including its anticipated impact on research at Uppsala University, with relevant units and staff within the University.	Vice Chancellor, disciplinary domains and/or and faculties	2026-ongoing
3. Consider strengthening alignment with ARRA's core commitments, while ensuring careful attention to disciplinary cultures and specific needs.	Disciplinary domains and/or faculties	2026-ongoing

Commitment 1: Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research

This section outlines actions aimed at broadening the recognition of diverse contributions, including open science and collaboration with wider society, and further developing strategic competence provision.

Action	Responsible unit(s)	Timeline
4. Develop and implement a university policy for open science.	Vice Chancellor, disciplinary domains and/or faculties	2025-2027
5. Define and apply criteria for recognising university–society collaboration in recruitment and promotion, tailored to disciplinary contexts.	Disciplinary domains and/or faculties	2025-ongoing
6. Investigate strategic competence provision	Assignment commissioned by the Vice Chancellor carried out by external investigator. Secretariat: Planning Division	2025-2026

Commitment 2: Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators

This section focuses on strengthening qualitative peer review practices and ensuring that assessment methods are rigorous and fit for purpose.

Action	Responsible unit(s)	Timeline
7. Enhance qualitative researcher assessment in recruitment by improving the consistency and quality of peer reviews, interviews, reference checks, and evaluation of personal and collaborative skills relevant to the position.	Disciplinary domains and/or faculties	2025-

Commitment 3: Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index

This section addresses the appropriate use of quantitative indicators by refining the University's allocation models, with due attention to disciplinary needs and the University's ambition to enhance its scientific impact. It further aims to broaden the coverage of bibliometric analyses.

Action	Responsible unit(s)	Timeline
8. Review of quantitative models for resource allocation across all organizational levels of the University (with consideration of the national framework governing the distribution of core funding).	Disciplinary domains and/or faculties and, for university-wide processes, the Vice Chancellor	2025-2027
9. Improve coverage in bibliometric analyses, including university-society collaboration by carefully considering new sources of scholarly metadata, following thorough examination and validation of the available options.	Planning Division and University Library	2025-2026

Commitment 4: Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

No actions are planned, as the University does not use rankings to assess research or researchers.

Follow-up and evaluation

Monitoring and evaluation of the action plan will take place within the disciplinary domains' established routines, during the annual quality dialogue between the Vice Chancellor and the Deputy Vice Chancellors, and as part of the University's regular research evaluations.

In line with CoARA, the University will also carry out a follow-up in 2029, five years after signing, focused on progress toward the agreement's four core commitments.